

**FOREIGN LANGUAGE LEARNING: THE STRATEGIES FOR TEACHER IN
LEARNER'S MOTIVATION**

**APPRENTISSAGE DES LANGUES ÉTRANGÈRES: DES STRATEGIES AUX
ENSEIGNANTS POUR MOTIVE LES APPRENANTS**

**APRENDIZAJE DE LENGUAS EXTRANJERAS: ESTRATEGIAS PARA QUE
LOS DOCENTS MOTIVE A LOS ALUMNUS**

**APRENDIZAGEM DE LÍNGUAS ESTRANGEIRAS: ESTRATÉGIAS PARA
QUE OS PROFESSORES MOTIVEM OS ALUNOS**

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this paper is to explore the literature on motivation in foreign language learning. It aims to propose strategies for teachers to motivate learners participate actively to the classroom learning activities, in order, to stimulate learners to take their learning more seriously and to raise teachers' awareness on the importance of motivating the learners in the classroom. Based on that, it is widely believed that among other individual differences in foreign language learning (personality, aptitude, learning style...) motivation is a complex phenomenon to deal with. Because when people have the desire to learn a language they engage in a community more effectively. Also, they feel more secure. Moreover, it synthesizes the conclusion draw from the literature on motivation conducted to identify appropriate strategies to be used by teachers in their classroom.

Key- words: strategies, teacher, motivation, learner.

Résumé: Le but de cet article est d'explorer la littérature sur la motivation dans l'apprentissage des langues étrangères, il vise à proposer des strategies aux enseignants pour motive les apprenants à participer activement aux activités d'apprentissage en classe, afin de stimuler les apprenants à prenda leur apprentissage plus au sérieux et de sensibiliser les enseignants à l'importance de motive les apprenants en classe.

Partant de là, il est largement admis que, parmi d' autres différences individuelles dans l'apprentissage des langues étrangères (personnalité, aptitude, style d'apprentissage...), la motivation est un phénomène complexe à gérer. Parce que lorsque les gens ont le désir d'apprendre une langue, ils s'engagent plus efficacement dans une communauté. De plus, ils se sentent plus en sécurité. De plus, il synthétise les conclusions tirées de la littérature sur la motivation menée pour identifier les stratégies appropriées à utiliser par les enseignants dans leur classe.

Mot-clé: stratégies, enseignant, motivation, apprenant.

RESUMEN

El propósito de este artículo es explorar la literatura sobre la motivación en el aprendizaje de lenguas extranjeras, su objetivo es proponer estrategias para que los docentes motive a los alumnos a participar activamente en las actividades de aprendizaje más en serio y concienciar a los docentes sobre la importancia de motivar a los alumnos en el aula. En base a esto, se cree ampliamente que, entre otras diferencias individuales en el aprendizaje de lenguas extranjeras (personalidad; aptitud, estilo de aprendizajes...), la motivación es un fenómeno complejo de abordar. Porque cuando las personas desean aprender un idioma, se involucran en una comunidad de manera más efectiva. Además, se sienten más seguros. Además, sintetiza las conclusiones extraídas de la literatura sobre motivación realizada para identificar estrategias apropiadas para ser utilizadas por los docentes en su aula.

Palabra-clave: estrategias, docente, motivación, alumno.

RESUMO

O propósito deste artigo é de explorar a literatura sobre motivação na aprendizagem de línguas estrangeiras. Tem como objetivo propor estratégias para que os professores motivem os alunos a participarem activamente nas actividades de aprendizagem em sala de aula, a fim de estimular os alunos a levarem a sua aprendizagem mais a sério e a consciencializar os professores sobre a importância de motivar os alunos. Com base nisso, acredita-se amplamente que, entre outras diferenças individuais na aprendizagem de línguas estrangeiras (personalidade, aptitude, estilo de aprendizagem etc.), a motivação é um fenómeno complexo de lidar. Quando as pessoas desejam aprender uma língua, elas se envolvem em uma comunidade de forma mais eficaz. Além disso, eles se sentem mais seguros. Além disso, sintetiza as conclusões extraídas da literatura sobre motivação realizada para identificar estratégias adequadas a serem utilizadas pelos professores em sala de aula.

Palavra-chave: estratégias, professor, motivação, aluno.

INTRODUCTION

Motivation has been used to stimulate learners to perform well in school. Nowadays, learners are motivated to learn and speak English for various purpose all over the world, particularly in Angola. It is interesting and challenging for the teachers to be reminded that this desire is achieved in a classroom. Admittedly, the learning of any foreign language requires the concept of motivation, because it is one of the key factors in order for people to have success. In this case, the main concern of this paper is on how teachers can encourage their learners to engage in class and have success when it comes to learning. It is quite impossible for learners to learn a language without being motivated. Motivation is an important contributor to language achievement in terms of linguistic outcomes. Which traditionally embrace the knowledge structure of the language, including listening, understanding, reading and writing, Gardner, (1985). This paper concluded with a call attention for teachers to focus more on learners' motivation using appropriate strategies to engage learners during the lesson.

The current study falls into the area of foreign language learning and focused on some teaching strategies for motivating students to learn English. It aims to propose strategies for teachers to motivate learners participate actively to the classroom learning activities. It has been stated the following research problem, learners show lack of motivation during the lessons by not participating actively to the classroom learning activities. On the base of the research problem, the research question were: what are the factors affecting learner's motivation? how can teacher ensure learner's motivation? What are the strategies that teacher can use to stimulate learners attention?. This study was restricted to teachers of non- speciality.

Theories of motivation and brief review of previous studies on motivation

In the field of language learning and teaching, motivation has been conceptualized from various perspectives. Before looking at some of the most prominent perspectives, it is important to clarify what motivation is. Despite its complex delineation, motivation has been referred to as the element responsible for why people decide to do something, how long they are willing to sustain the activity, and how hard they are going to pursue it, (Dörnyei, 2014, p.519).

As Gardner (1985) puts it, motivation involves four aspects, namely, a goal, effortful behavior, a desire to attain the goal and favorable attitudes toward the activity in question' (p. 50). Without these aspects, it is almost impossible to achieve a certain degree of motivation. Moreover, Gass et al. (2020) clarify that 'whereas aptitude indicates one's potential, whatever that might be, is determined in a large part by motivation' (p. 522). Concluding, Dörnyei (2014) posits that conceptualizing motivation can be problematic since human behavior may be influenced and shaped by internal factors (e.g., individual curiosity, or interest), and by external factors (e.g., the relationship within language communities and classroom dynamics). Next, we look briefly at some theories around motivation and previous studies.

Self-determination theory

According to Ryan and Deci (2000), self-determination theory is focused on the social-contextual conditions that facilitate versus forestall the natural processes of self-motivation and healthy psychological development. Specifically, factors have been examined that enhance versus undermine intrinsic motivation, self-regulation, and well-being. (p.1). According to Deci and Ryan (1985), this theory highlights two types of motivation: intrinsic motivation (e.g., learning because of personal drive), and extrinsic motivation (i.e., learning for external rewards or pressure) Deci and Ryan (1985).

Deci and Ryan (1985) argue that there are three psychological needs that when fulfilled may enhance motivation to learning and mental health. These psychological needs are:

- **competence**; refers to the feeling of control of one's own learning process.
- **Autonomy**; has to do with the feeling of being able to achieve success in learning tasks.
- **Relatedness**; is concerned with connection to others. For example, teachers, classmates, members of the target language, and so forth.

In language classes, teachers may promote learners' autonomy by providing opportunities for learners to make decisions on their own regarding the tasks, order of completion, books to read, and even leading some lessons, whereas teachers can respond to the learners' competence needs by using material that matches the learners' proficiency levels and skills. For examples, using material that is too difficult will decrease the sense of competence in learners, while using material that is too easy will decrease the learners' chances to learn. Teachers can also provide a classroom environment that offers learners immediate feedback for their performance. Teachers can respond to learners' relatedness needs by creating cooperative classroom environment. Teachers can encourage learners to work in a small groups or pairs. This will provide learners with opportunities to work together and create a sense of a learning community. In terms of research, according to Noel et al., (2023), learners' motivation may be assessed by using the intrinsic and extrinsic subcategory introduced by Deci and Ryan (1985) and Vallerand et al. (1989, 1992, 1993).

Expectancy-value theory

According to Leaper (2011), this theory claims that achievement-related choices are motivated by a combination of people's expectations for success and subjective task value in particular domains. (p. 359). This concept is also applied in language learning. In fact, language learners are also more prone to participate in language tasks when they perceive a sense of competence and find its content relatable. According to the expectancy-value model, expectations for success and task value are shaped by a combination of factors. These include child characteristics (abilities, previous experiences, goals, self-concepts, beliefs, expectations, interpretations) and environmental influences (cultural milieu, socializers' beliefs and behaviors), Leaper (2011). Several research studies have found that expectation for success and task value are correlated. Expectation for success are likely to predict learners' task value. In other

words, learners are mostly to value the tasks or domains of tasks they feel more competent about (Eccles and Wigfield, 2002; Rosenzweig et al., 2019; Wigfield and Eccles, 2001). These findings have pedagogical implications in that teachers should design tasks that are accessible to the level of learners so that they can experience some degree of success and be motivated to carry on with the tasks at hand.

Second language motivational self-system.

It has been put forward by Dörnyei (2005; 2009) and expanded by research studies conducted by several scholars. According to Dörnyei (2014), the second language motivational self-system is 'rooted in important psychological concept of possible selves, which represents people's ideas of what they might become, what they would like to become, and what they are afraid of becoming (p. 521). Dörnyei (2014) contends that 'possible selves are more than mere long-term goals or future plans in that they involve tangible images and senses (p. 521) and adds that individuals who have well developed possible self can imagine this self in vibrant and realistic future situations.

Accordingly, Dörnyei (2014) outlines three components of the second language motivational self-system and provides the following conception for each of them:

- **ideal second language self;** which refers to the second language-specific facet of the learner's ideal self.
- **Ought-to second language self;** which concerns the attributes that learner believes that they need to have or avoid possible negative outcomes and that, therefore, may bear little resemblance to their own desires or wishes.
- **Second language learning experience;** which refers to learner's situation-specific motives related to the immediate learning environment and experience.

In addition to these three constitutes, Dörnyei (2014) presents a series of conditions for motivational power of vision. Among other prerequisites, he argues that vision-enhancing strategies are geared if the learner has a desired future self-image; the learner's future self is sufficiently different from current self; the learner's future self-image is elaborated and vivid; the learner's future image is perceived and possible (for a thorough discussion see Dörnyei, 2009; 2014).

What are the factors affecting students' motivation?

Teacher's classroom management skill

One of the most critical factors determining learners' motivation, according to Yilmaz et al. (2017), is the teacher's classroom management skill. Effective classroom management, in general, is a practice that improves learner's independent learning abilities, productivity, and achievement, with the primary goal of preventing interruptions to the teaching and learning process and allowing it to continue in a well-organized teaching and learning environment.

Ensuring learners' motivation in the classroom

Learner's motivation can be ensured in 3 ways, and this is according to Ur. (2012)

1. By taking every opportunity to show them how important it is for them to know English.

In today's world, English provides extensive opportunities for further studies and possible employment. For leisure time activities and entertainment, and perhaps most significant for teenagers and young adults' social interaction with people from other cultures and language, whether online or face to face.

2. By fostering their self-image as successful language learners

We can do our best to make sure they succeed in tasks and give them tests only when we are sure they will be able to perform well. Teachers need to be careful to provide negative or corrective feedback tactfully and supportively, taking every opportunity to praise and encourage.

3. By ensuring that classroom activities are interesting

It is not enough that tasks are communicative or that texts are interesting. Teachers need to employ a number of strategies in task design and administration that can help to create and maintain learner interest in doing them for example, using game-like activities.

Motivation in the classroom

This is the most critical part for teachers to engage learners in the most critical part for teachers to engage students in the learning process. Lightbrown and Spada (2006, p. 64) say that, in a teacher's mind, motivated students are usually those who participate actively in class, express interest in the subject matter, and study a great deal.

From this view, it can clearly be understood that learners' participation in classroom activities marks the beginning of motivation to accomplish certain tasks. Teachers also have more influence on these behaviors and motivation they represent than on learners'. Reasons for studying the foreign language or their attitudes toward the language and its speakers. Teachers can make a positive contribution to learners enjoy coming to, because the content is interesting and relevant to their age and level of ability, the learning goals are challenging yet manageable and clear, and the atmosphere is supportive.

Bearing in mind the quotation above, it can be emphasized that teachers have a huge job in the classroom. Furthermore, students see them as a great source for their success. In a nutshell, it is their job to stimulate learners if they want to maintain good atmosphere in the classroom. Crookes & Schmidt (1991), pointed out the following strategies;

1. **Motivating learners in the class into a lesson;** teachers should encourage learners each and every day they are in the class to stimulate their participation in the class.

2. **Varying the activities, tasks and materials;** teachers have to think of different activities whenever they are in the classroom. If learners perform single activity in the class this can also decrease their attention and they become bored. Furthermore, in respect of activities, there are times when teachers have to tell learners to speak or listen to the information and so forth. In respect of tasks. Finally, materials to learners, such

as; worksheets, textbooks and many others. Thus, varying activities, tasks and materials have great impact on learners learning maintenance.

3. **Using co-operative rather than competitive goal;** one of the techniques to increase learners' motivation is by putting them work in pairs or groups. This is also one way to encourage weaker learners to speak or even take risk when they are given tasks to perform, and by doing so, learners become more confident in learning.

Analyse and discussion about the conceptual framework of motivation

Motivation plays a paramount role in the learning of a foreign language, that is the reason why teachers always strives to use strategies to create, maintain and protect motivation (Kirondo 2014, p.25). From the figure below we can realise that best strategies with positive perception of motivation to learn bring positive results to students provided that all necessary factors which might interfere this are controlled. Otherwise, with positive perception and good strategies but with limiting factors the intended results will not be attained. Despite those efforts several factors impede the use of these strategies as shown in the Figure below:

Conceptual Framework

Source: Field Data (2013) cited in Odango (2014)

Knowing something without practising or applying it is like filling a bottle with a lot of holes, the result is known by all of us that it is like doing nothing. Strategies must be applied correctly so that the students get motivated and show interest to participate in classroom activities and better their learning. Motivation is really important for anyone who wants to achieve or reach to a goal in life, in the case of EFL classroom, the idea is to get the students to speak the language being taught but it is known that without any motivation it is almost impossible to do something because that driving force serves as a scaffolding. And it becomes an indispensable ingredient to involve students in different environments to use the language. English language teachers should make use of the different strategies, like varying activities in the class, varying materials, put them to work together and so on... (Crookes and Schmidt 1991) so that motivation can become a reality among students of non speciality.

All students are motivated to learn and speak English because it is an international language and the most used worldwide, consequently most of instruction is in English, then students should learn how to communicate in English. In short, students believe that teachers can motivate them if some strategies are applied and, anticipate rewards during lessons, these students would be more enthusiastic and more interested to learn what is being taught.

CONCLUSION

This paper explored some theories of motivation strategies and factors affecting learners' motivation in the classroom. Bearing in mind that teachers play significant roles in increasing or decreasing learners' motivation, this paper also proposed to teachers different ways to ensure learners' motivation. Therefore, teachers would find it so helpful to use these strategies in their classroom in order to motivate learners when it comes to learning English as a foreign language so that they know how important it is to study this language, not only for their academic purposes, but also for their life career.

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